

THE CIRCULAR RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INCOME INEQUALITY AND FINANCE

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Abstract

The relationships between finance and inequality are numerous, complex and intertwined. On the one hand, the impact of finance on inequality is difficult to pin down: there is as yet no academic consensus as to the sign of the relationship, with results varying widely depending on whether we focus on the size of the financial sector or on other more such as deregulation, or the role of banks. In any case, it appears that the impact is highly dependent on the country's institutional context. In the absence of solid institutions, the development of finance can be an opportunity for certain interest groups to capture rents, with negative consequences in terms of inequality.

Keywords: Inequality- Finance- Development- Opportunity.

INTRODUCTION

The increase in income and wealth inequalities has taken on a growing role in public debate, with intensity redoubled since the 2013 publication of *Le Capital* in the 21st century by Thomas Piketty. Several years earlier, the latter's work (see, among others, Piketty, 2003 and 2013; Atkinson et al., 2011) had already highlighted the rise in the share of total income captured by the wealthiest 1%, as well as the growing concentration of wealth over recent decades, in developed countries, but also in some emerging economies. Stiglitz (2012) also warned of the significant cost of rising inequality in the United States. More unexpectedly, there have been calls to blame these growing inequalities for over-indebtedness among the population. and poor households that led to the financial crisis of 2007-2008. In particular, the debate gained momentum following contributions by Rajan (2010) and Galbraith (2012), both of whom argued that rising income inequality in the US had forced low- and middle-income households to take on more debt in order to maintain their consumption levels.

This article reviews the literature on the links between income inequality dynamics and credit expansion. Rising inequality has occurred in parallel with rapid growth in private indebtedness. The latter was identified as a major determinant of the 2007-2008 financial crisis in the United States (Greenwood and Scharfstein, 2013). But this joint rise in inequality and credit has also been observed for many other countries, as shown in graphs 1a to 1d (infra). This convergence of trends became evident in the 1990s, particularly in the second half of the decade.

This very strong correlation may, however, have multiple explanations, given the numerous and complex theoretical relationships between credit and inequality. In fact, the academic literature on the links between these two variables points to the existence of a probable circularity. In addition, other phenomena, including public policies affecting the regulatory frameworks of the labor market and the financial sphere, are likely to have an impact on both inequality and credit, making it even more difficult to identify causal links. The diagram below summarizes the main channels that will be discussed in detail in this article.

First, we'll look at the impact of finance on inequality. The term "finance" here refers both to the quantity of credit distributed to economic agents and to the regulatory framework governing the activity of the financial sphere, these two dimensions being at the heart of most university analyses on the subject³. Until recently, the benchmark studies (Levine, 2005; Beck et al., 2007) concluded that the quantitative expansion of the financial sphere had a positive impact on reducing inequality, as it should improve access to credit for the poorest. However, this result has been called into question by analyses showing possible non-linear effects, pointing to the existence of a threshold beyond which the relationship reverses (Greenwood and Jovanovic, 1990). The initial level of economic development and the rent-seeking behavior of elites (Claessens and Perotti, 2007) may also influence the relationship. In addition to the quantity of credit, financial liberalization in its many dimensions (reduced government control over the financial sphere) can also have an impact.

Banking and finance, which is supposed to lead to a higher degree of effective competition in the sector, open up stock markets, reduce or abolish controls on international capital movements, etc.), which generates all the more inequality the weaker the country's institutional development. Finance can also have a negative impact on income distribution, due to the high level of wages in the financial sector (Philippon and Resheff, 2012) or if credit expansion provokes a financial crisis (Baldacci et al., 2002; Maarek and Orgiazzi, 2013; Meyer and Sullivan, 2013).

Graphics 1

Household credit (as % of GDP) and inequality (Top 1%)

Chart 1a: United States

Chart 1b: France

Chart 1c: China

Chart 1d: Spain

Sources for the four graphs: WID (World Wealth and Income Database); Bank for International Settlements (BIS).

In the second part, we look at the other direction of causality, from inequality to credit. We distinguish between the credit demand channel and the credit supply channel. With regard to the latter, a central argument is that the institutional environment, via both financial liberalization and monetary policy, has enabled financial institutions to grant more credit, notably to riskier households (Atkinson and Morelli, 2010; Rajan, 2010). However, the existence of a causal link is not always obvious. Rising inequality and financial expansion may well have been the joint product of liberalization policies pursued for over thirty years, without the former having influenced the latter. The demand channel, on the other hand, focuses on the reaction of households to negative income shocks: the stagnation or relative decline in income of the working and middle classes may have led them to increase their indebtedness in order to maintain their standard of living. The literature suggests various mechanisms, such as cognitive ones, to understand why households may perceive this shock as transitory.

In this respect, while empirical studies were initially divided as to the existence of a causal link between inequality and credit, results have recently accumulated in favor of a positive impact of the former on the latter. Using an original identification strategy, we confirm the existence of a positive causal link and emphasize the differentiated impact according to the income levels considered. In particular, we show that income shocks affecting the middle classes are likely to explain a significant part of this relationship. We discuss these results in greater detail at the end of the article, before concluding.

Diagram

Complex relationships between inequality, private debt and financial crises

Source: authors' research.

WHAT IMPACT DOES FINANCE HAVE ON INEQUALITY?

It is important here to distinguish between the effects of (1) credit growth (size of the financial sector, which can be characterized as quantitative financial development), (2) financial deregulation (qualitative financial development) and (3) financial crises. Each of these three dimensions will have a very different impact on the level of inequality.

Financial development, financial deregulation and inequality

Through information asymmetries and transaction costs, credit constraints have a significant impact on the health of our customers of economic agents. They hit the poorest households hardest, as they have no collateral and suffer the most discrimination when it comes to granting credit. In theory, financial development should benefit the poorest first, by relaxing this constraint and improving capital allocation, thereby reducing inequalities. This idea of a linear and positive relationship between financial development and inequality was first widely accepted in economic literature, particularly in development economics (Banerjee and Newman, 1993; Galor and Zeira, 1993). Levine (2005, p. 920) sums up this apparent consensus: "The results indicate that finance has a disproportionately positive impact on the poor and contributes to reducing inequalities." Thus, according to Beck et al (2007), financial development has a positive impact on the poorest quintile of households, with 60% of this effect explained by a growth effect and 40% by a redistributive effect. Several other studies support this result (Clarke et al., 2006; Enowbi Batuo et al., 2010; Kappel, 2010; Mookerjee and Kalipioni, 2010).

However, this certainty has been called into question by several studies showing ambiguous effects⁴. The relationship between financial development and inequality could be non-linear. Kim and Lin (2011) show that financial development reduces inequality only beyond a certain threshold of financial market depth. Law and Tan (2012), using another inequality database⁵, also find non-linearity, but in the opposite direction to Kim and Lin (2011). For them, financial development reduces inequality for low levels of financial development, but tends to increase it for higher levels. Finally, Jauch and Watzka (2011), in an empirical analysis of 138 countries over the period 1960-2008, find a positive effect of financial development on inequality. According to their estimates, a 10% increase in credit would raise the Gini coefficient by 0.23. Another recent dent in the belief that financial development is systematically beneficial to reducing inequality, Denk and Cournède's (2015) analysis for various periods between 1974 and 2011 concludes that the expansion of the financial sphere (represented by private credit, the share of value added generated by the financial sector and the size of stock markets) has fuelled income inequality in OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) countries.

Financial deregulation (qualitative financial development) does not have the same effects as the simple quantitative development of the financial sphere. Claessens and Perotti (2007) show that financial liberalization can increase inequality when institutions are too weak to prevent rent capture. This result is confirmed by empirical research. Focusing on the case of India, Ang (2010) shows that (quantitative) financial development is likely to reduce inequalities, but that financial liberalization in itself tends to exacerbate them. But in the US

case, Beck et al (2010) show that financial liberalization over the period 1976-2006 tended to reduce inequality (by 3% to 10%). These different results may be explained by the very different institutional development of the two countries. It should be noted, however, that the results might have been different if this study of the United States had taken into account the effects of the 2007-2008 financial crisis (the period considered ends in 2006) - a point to which we return in the next section. In a study of forty-nine countries over the 1994-2002 period, Gimet and Lagoarde-Segot (2011) also confirm that the distributive consequences of financial liberalization depend largely on the institutional conditions in which it is implemented.

Another dimension to consider is the effect of high wages in finance on inequality. Philippon and Reshef (2012) show that employees in the US financial sector are paid 50% more than those in the non-financial sector, for the same characteristics. This would explain between 15% and 25% of the rise in inequality observed since the early 1990s. Denk (2015) shows a similar effect for the European Union, but of lesser magnitude (28% higher wages in the financial sector on average). In a study of sixteen developed and emerging countries, Roine et al (2009) show that the size of the financial sector has a positive impact on the share of income held by the wealthiest 1%. The impact is insignificant for the richest 1%- 10%, and negative for the poorest 90%. Finally, Hein (2015) links the more general concept of financialization to inequality. He shows that this phenomenon tends to reduce labor's share of value added through three channels: (1) a change in the sectoral composition of the economy, (2) a rise in management salaries and profit requirements, and (3) a weakening of unions' bargaining power.

The results of the literature on the effects of finance on inequality are summarized in Table 1 (below).

Table 1: The impact of financial development on inequality

Articles	Dependent variable	Measuring financial development	Main result
Ang (2010)	Gini	Private credit/GDP, (M3 - M1)/GDP	[-3 % ; -0,4 %]
Ang (2010)	Gini	Liberalization index financial	[+0,2 % ; +0,7 %]
Arora (2012)	Gini	Private credit or loans personnel/GDP, number of branches banking/population	Development is driving up(lower) inequalities in urban areas (rural)
Beck et al (2007)	Growth rates of the Gini	Private credit/GDP	[-0.05; -0.1] points
Beck et al (2007)	Growth rate of population share living with 1 dollar/day	Private credit/GDP	-0.5 points
Beck et al (2010)	Gini and Theil	1 when the State authorizes entry of a subsidiary banking, 0 otherwise	[-3 % ; -2 %]
Beck et al (2010)	90/10 ratio and 75/25 ratio	1 when the State authorizes entry of a subsidiary banking, 0 otherwise	[-10 % ; -7 %]
Clarke et al (2006)	Gini	Private credit/GDP	-3 %

Enowbi Bano <i>et al.</i> (2010)	Gini	Liquid liabilities/GDP, M2/GDP, private credit/GDP	[-0,5 % ; -0,2 %]
Denk (2015)	Gini	Employment in the sector financial	Jobs in finance explains the higher Gini by 0.8 points. The financial salaries are 28% on average higher.
Denk and Cournède (2015)	Gini	Private credit/GDP, capitalization stock market/GDP	[+0.11; +0.13] points
Gimet and Lagoarde-Segot (2011)	Gini	Private credit/GDP, spread, financial industry export	Positive causal impact of financial development on inequality, which depends characteristics sector
Jauch and Watzka (2011)	Gini	Private credit/GDP, bank deposits/GDP	+0.23 points
Kappel (2010)	Gini	Private credit/GDP, capitalization stock market/GDP	[-2; -1] points
Kim and Lin (2011)	Growth rates of the Gini	Private credit/GDP, liquid liabilities/GDP, banking assets/GDP	[+2 %; +3 %] when low level intermediation financial [-12 % ; -7 %] when high level intermediation
Law and Tan (2009)	Gini	Private credit/GDP, capitalization stock market/GDP	0 (no impact)
Law and Tan (2009)	Gini	Private credit/GDP, liquid liabilities/GDP	Non-linear effects, but quantitatively very low
Mookerjee and Kalipioni (2010)	Gini	Number of branches banking for 100,000 inhabitants	Negative impact on inequalities, but difficult to interpret quantitatively
Philippon and Reshef (2012)	Gini	Financial industry and financial salaries	Salaries in the finance would explain 15%-25% of increase in wage inequality since 1980 in the United States
Roine <i>et al.</i> (2009)	Top 1% sales	Banking sectors and stock	+1 standard deviation (50% of GDP) leads to

Note: for each item, this table reports the main estimataerskceot/nGceDrnPing the relationship between a certain dependent variable and a measure of financial development. Unless o+t0h.e5rwpoisientstTaotepd1, the figures presented correspond to a variation of 10% in the financial development variable under consideration, or a movement from 0 to 1 in the case of a binary variable. Where estimates are too numerous and/or a quantitative assessment proves impossible, qualitative interpretations are reported.

Source: authors' research.

Financial crises and inequality

Financial crises have specific and heterogeneous effects, depending on the type of crisis under consideration (banking crisis, currency crisis, twin crises). The first distributive effect of crises is their impact on GDP. Like any shock affecting growth, financial crises will have

diverse (and ambiguous) effects on income distribution and inequality (Bourguignon, 2004). The consequences of financial crises depend on the size of the financial sector, which is directly correlated with the severity of the crisis. Additional distributional effects can be observed, particularly in terms of the impact on employment, which is likely to have a greater impact on poorer populations. Particularly in developing countries, a financial crisis may lead to job losses in the formal sector, reducing demand for informal sector services. The increase in the supply of informal labor linked to the loss of formal employment can lead to increased underemployment and lower wages (Baldacci et al., 2002). Baldacci et al. (2002) identify three other channels through which crises impact on poverty and inequality: changes in relative prices, fiscal austerity and changes in asset values. On the first point, financial crises are often accompanied by sharp depreciations in the exchange rate: these lead to an increase in demand for goods in the tradable sector, which in turn increases employment and wages in the tradable sector. The opposite phenomenon occurs in the non-tradable goods sector, where activity falls and workers become poorer. The poorest may also be affected by the rising price of imported goods, particularly food. Secondly, crises are often followed by severe periods of fiscal austerity, characterized by a contraction in public spending, primarily affecting social spending, which amplifies the initial impact of the shock on the poor. Finally, variations in interest rates, real estate and financial asset prices following financial crises often have a significant impact on the incomes of the wealthiest, who depend to a large extent on their assets.

Galbraith and Jianqing (1999) focus on the distributional impact of currency crises. They show that the average increase in inequality two years after a crisis is 16.2%, compared with 3.2% in the absence of crises. They also note that inequality increases more when the labor market is deregulated.

Morelli (2014) studies the impact of systemic banking crises and shows a weak impact on the richest 10% in the United States. But this weak average effect masks a heterogeneous effect within this population. The effect tends to be negative for very high incomes (the richest 0.01%), while it is positive for those below this threshold. This result is consistent with that of Roine et al (2009) on a larger sample of countries, which shows a negative correlation with the share of income held by the richest 1%, while the relationship is insignificant for the rest of the top decile. Differences in the composition of income for these different individuals are likely to explain this heterogeneity: the share of capital income is higher for the wealthiest 1%, while labor income accounts for the largest share for those below them.

A second stream of literature focuses on the respective shares of labor and capital in value added. Diwan (2001) shows that currency crises are associated with a decline in the share of labor in total income. Maarek and Orgiazzi (2013) obtain a similar result in an analysis of the manufacturing sector in twenty advanced countries. Exchange rate crises reduce the labor share by 2 percentage points on average. Bazillier and Najman (2017) obtain an effect of the same magnitude on a sample of advanced and developing countries and for all sectors. On the other hand, the effects are very different for banking crises, which initially have a negative impact on the capital share, particularly at the onset of the crisis. This effect

is stronger in OECD countries. Table 2 (below) summarizes the findings of the literature on the direct impact of financial crises on inequality.

The 2007-2008 crisis has also led to progress in understanding the distributive effects of crises, which can come through more indirect channels linked to fiscal policies. Jenkins et al (2013) study the country- by-country effects within the OECD. They find few direct effects on income distribution in the two years following the crisis (2007-2009). Nevertheless, it seems that social protection systems and counter- cyclical policies implemented at the start of the crisis played a major role in this result. Fiscal consolidation policies certainly had a greater anti-redistributive effect. This intuition is confirmed by Ball et al (2013), who show a clear positive correlation between the level of inequality and these consolidation policies. These policies also reduce labor's share of value added and increase long-term unemployment. Woo et al (2013) estimate the effect of a budget contraction of 1 percentage point of GDP to be a 0.4%-0.7% increase in the Gini coefficient in the first two years. 15%-20% of this rise in inequality can be explained by the rise in unemployment directly attributable to fiscal austerity policies.

Table 2: The impact of financial crises on inequality

Articles	Dependent variable	Measuring the crisis	Main result
Bal <i>et al</i> (2013)	Gini, labor share in VA, unemployment long-term	Consolidation budget	Consolidation, consecutive budget to a crisis leads to rising inequality and long-term unemployment. In the long term, a of work in VA
Baldacci <i>et al.</i> (2002)	Gini, income by quantile, rate of poverty most	Currency crises	Positive impact on the Gini and the poverty. The 2 nd quantile income is affected
Baldacci <i>et al.</i> (2002)	Poverty, income by level	Mexican crisis	Increase in poverty and the gap of poverty, but falls significant inequalities
Bazillier <i>et Najman</i> (2017)	Labour share in income	Banking crises and foreign exchange	[-2%; -2.5%] for the 3 years following currency crisis, 0 for banking crises
Diwan (2001)	Labour share in income	Currency crises	-5% during the crisis, -2.6% for 3 subsequent years
Galbraith and Jiaqing (1999)	Indices Theil for income	Currency crises	+16.2% in the 2 years following a crises
Jenkins <i>et al</i> (2013)	Gross disposable income households	Financial crisis 2007-2008	0 (no impact)
Maarek and Orgiazzi (2013)	Labour share in income	Currency crises	-2 %
Meyer and Sullivan (2013)	90/10 ratio (in terms of revenue)	Financial crisis 2007-2008	+1 point in 3 years after the crisis
Meyer and Sullivan (2013)	90/10 ratio (in terms of consumption)	Financial crisis 2007-2008	-0.2 points in 3 years after the crisis

Morelli (2014)	Top income 0.01	Banking systemic crises	[-1 % ; -0,5 %]
Morelli (2014)	Top income 10% - Top 5% income	Banking systemic crises	[+0,7 % ; +0,9 %]
Morelli (2014)	Top 10% income	Banking systemic crises	0 (no impact)
Park <i>et al</i> (2012)	Income by category of workers	Financial crisis 2007-2008	Workers low-skilled are most affected
Roine <i>et al</i> (2009)	Top 1% income	Banking and financial exchange (indicators binary)	Banking crises: -1.1% for Top 1%; currency crises: 0
Roine <i>et al</i> (2009)	Top income 10% - Top 1% income	Banking and financial exchange (indicators binary)	Banking crises: 0 ; currency crises: 0
Woo <i>et al</i> (2013)	Gini	Consolidation	[+0.4%; -0.7%] 2 years after

Note: for each article, the table reports the main estimates concerning the relationship between a certain dependent variable and a financial crisis measure. When the estimates are too numerous and/or a quantitative assessment is impossible, qualitative interpretations are reported.

Source: authors' research.

Finance (in the broadest sense) therefore has strong distributive impacts. These effects are complex and ambiguous. To disentangle them, we need to distinguish between the effects of increased credit and those of financial deregulation and crises. The latter, in turn, have very heterogeneous effects, depending on the type of crisis considered and the response of economic policies to these crises. We now turn our attention to the other direction of the causal relationship between finance and inequality, focusing on the effects of the latter on private indebtedness, particularly that of households.

THE IMPACT OF INEQUALITY ON PRIVATE DEBT

As summarized in the diagram above, inequalities are likely to have an effect on credit through two channels: the credit demand channel and the credit supply channel. With regard to the demand channel, the main issue is to determine the nature (transient or permanent) of the income shock faced by households. With regard to the supply of credit, the challenge is to distinguish the causal effect from any so-called coincidental factors (financial liberalization and monetary policy in particular).

The demand channel: what kind of income shock?

The first type of analysis refers to transitory income shocks. Krueger and Perri (2011) insist that credit can be used to smooth consumption in the event of income shocks. In another article based on U.S. data, Krueger and Perri (2006) show that the rise in income inequality in the U.S. observed in the last twenty-five years had not led to a subsequent rise in

consumption inequality. They deduce that this rise in inequality is explained by increased volatility in transitory income, with no impact on permanent income. This increased volatility would explain most of the credit growth observed since 1980. In a similar vein, Iacoviello (2008) proposes a dynamic model to explain the joint rise in inequality and credit. As with Krueger and Perri (2006), he shows that it is income volatility, rather than permanent income shocks, that explains credit growth.

The assumption that rising inequality reflects transitory shocks has been widely challenged (Van Treeck, 2014). Kopczuk et al (2010) show that social mobility has decreased, which contradicts the hypothesis of greater individual income volatility. Moffitt and Gottschalk (2002 and 2011) also find that the variance of transitory income tended to decline after 1980, unlike that of permanent income.

If income shocks affecting households are permanent, they should theoretically adjust their consumption without resorting to borrowing (Piketty and Saez, 2013)⁸. It is therefore necessary to understand why this adjustment has not taken place. An initial explanation is provided by Bertrand and Morse (2013), who point out that households cannot fully adjust their consumption to their income when the shock affecting the latter proves too great, and the welfare loss associated with the induced drop in consumption too great.

A second explanation relates to the possibility that households define their level of consumption by taking into account that of other economic agents. It has been known since Veblen (1899) that satisfaction with a given level of consumption also depends on the consumption of other social groups (later referred to as the "keeping up with the Joneses" phenomenon). Van Treeck (2014) considers this to be the main reason behind high consumption trajectories for the poorest and middle classes, despite stagnating incomes. This is what Frank et al. (2014) refer to as the spending cascade: income growth among the richest leads, by mimetic effect, to higher consumption among the lower social groups.

This argument is close to that of Atkinson and Morelli (2011), who consider that the rise in credit is essentially explained by a desire on the part of the poorest households and the middle classes to maintain their standard of living in a context of falling real or relative incomes. The evolution of indebtedness by income level supports this argument. Kumhof et al (2015) point out that that in the USA in 1983, the richest 5% had a much higher debt ratio (around 15%) than the poorest 95%. In 2007, the debt ratio of the poorest 95% was twice that of the richest 5%.

A final argument of a similar nature is based on the structural insufficiency of aggregate demand, the result of too high a level of inequality (Atkinson and Morelli, 2011), preventing most individuals, too impoverished, from consuming sufficiently. This is a very old argument, dating back to Malthus (1836), who devoted a chapter of his book to the theories of under-consumption. Galbraith (1954) identified income distribution as the main weakness of the United States before the 1929 crisis, using the same argument. Debt was the only way for agents to maintain consumption at a sufficient level, and thus sustain aggregate demand in a context of high inequality.

The supply channel: what impact does the institutional environment have?

The first theoretical argument, recently formalized by Kumhof et al. (2015), establishes a direct causal link of rising inequality, materialized in the form of a permanent transfer of income to the wealthiest, on the supply of credit. The increase in high incomes leads to a rise in the savings of the households concerned, recycled directly into the supply of credit. Lysandrou (2011) relies on a similar mechanism. The rise in total savings enables an accumulation of private wealth, which in turn induces increased demand for financial securities, pulling up the supply of credit. This ever-growing stock of capital must then be lent out, including to riskier borrowers, which is made easy by the use of complex financial products.

The second argument in favor of explaining credit supply is more indirect. Financial institutions could have been encouraged to lend to riskier individuals. This is the main argument of Rajan (2010, p. 43): "Rising inequality in the U.S. induced political pressure to increase housing credit. This pressure has created a serious fault line that has led to major distortions in the financial sector." So it's the political environment that explains the link between inequality and credit: the guarantee offered by the US federal government through the Federal National Mortgage Association (FNMA, nicknamed Fannie Mae) and the Federal Home Loan Mortgage Corporation (FHLMC, nicknamed Freddie Mac) encouraged a substantial increase in home loans distributed to the poorest, giving the illusion for a time that this dynamic was sustainable, particularly in a context of expansionary monetary policy keeping interest rates at very low levels.

On the contrary, other researchers believe that institutional or political changes may explain a joint rise in inequality and credit, without there being any link between the two phenomena other than similar origins. For Atkinson and Morelli (2010), Krugman (2010), or Acemoglu (2011), these phenomena may be the joint result of the liberalization policies pursued since the 1980s. We must also take into account the potential impact of monetary policies, which obviously determine the volume of credit, but can also have significant distributional impacts (Coibion et al., 2017).

Empirically measuring the impact of inequality on credit

The complexity of the theoretical mechanisms linking inequality and credit and the existence of possible circular relationships make it difficult to empirically analyze the causal link between the two phenomena. In this regard, a recent article (Bazillier and Héricourt, 2017a) highlights three main empirical challenges: the treatment of endogeneity, the measurement of inequality, and the relevant measurement of credit.

Bordo and Meissner (2012) analyze the link between income inequality, credit growth and financial crises in a sample of fourteen advanced countries over the period 1920-2008. They find no impact of inequality (measured by the share of income held by the richest 1%) on total credit. However, their analysis does not take endogeneity issues into account, and focuses on total (bank) credit rather than household credit. Based on survey data from the Eurosystem Household Finance and Consumption Survey for 2010 alone, the study by

Cournède and Denk (2015) calculates the share of household credit by income distribution quintile. It appears that households at the bottom of the distribution do not account for a greater share of total credit in the most unequal countries. Like Bordo and Meissner (2012), the analysis therefore leads to the conclusion that inequality has no impact on credit in eurozone countries, but may be subject to the same criticisms regarding the lack of treatment of endogeneity. Moreover, their methodology, limited to a single year, with twelve countries as the only source of heterogeneity, is purely descriptive. It therefore does not allow us to go beyond a preliminary correlation study, causal inference not being the primary object of the analysis in question.

These results are contradicted by Perugini et al (2016) in an analysis of eighteen OECD countries over the period 1970-2007. Although their estimation strategy is open to discussion⁹, their study has the merit of addressing the issue of endogeneity, which can arise either from reverse causality, or from the existence of unobserved variables likely to be correlated with the two dimensions studied. They conclude that inequality (also measured by the share of income held by the richest) has a positive effect on credit (here measured by the ratio of private credit to GDP). An interesting aspect of this latest study is its consideration of the role of financial liberalization, which can be a factor fuelling both credit and inequality. While the authors highlight the role of liberalization on the volume of credit, they find a specific and additional effect of inequality. Analyses focusing specifically on the United States produce more uncertain results as to the type of credit at the source of the causal relationship. Christen and Morgan (2005) analyze the determinants of household credit between 1980 and 2003. They found a positive impact of inequality on credit, more marked for non-revolving loans and weaker for mortgages. Conversely, Yamarik et al (2016), using data from fifty US states over the period 1977-2010, find a strong causal impact of inequality on total household lending, this time driven by home loans.

Table 3: The impact of inequality on credit

Articles	Dependent variables	Measuring inequality	Main result
Bordo and Meissner (2012)	Log(bank credit to the private sector)	Top 1% sales	0 (no impact)
Perugini <i>et al</i> (2016)	Private credit/GDP	Top 1% sales	[+4 % ; +11 %]
Perugini <i>et al</i> (2016)	Private credit/GDP	Top 5	[+2,5 % ; +5 %]
Perugini <i>et al</i> (2016)	Private credit/GDP	Top 10	[+2 % ; +4,5 %]
Christen and Morgan (2005)	Household debt	Gini	+0,36 %
Yamarika <i>et al</i> (2016)	Mortgages/person al income	Top 1% sales	[0 % ; +16 %]
Yamarika <i>et al</i> (2016)	Mortgages/person al income	Gini	[+0,3 % ; +0,9 %]

Note: for each article, the table shows the main estimates of the relationship between a certain dependent variable and a measure of inequality. For the Gini index, the estimate presented corresponds to a positive variation of 1 point. For all other inequality measures, the coefficients reported refer to a 10% variation in the variable under consideration.

Source: authors' research.

In a recent study (Bazillier et al., 2017a and b), we propose a methodology for clearly identifying the existence of a causal relationship between inequality dynamics and household credit. This study covers forty-one countries between 1970 and 2014 and uses data from the BIS and the World Income Inequality Database (WIID, see box below). We focus on total household credit, an indicator that seems more relevant than an aggregate of total credit to the economy, given a theoretical background that largely emphasizes the dynamics of household debt - on the other hand, we are unable to distinguish between different types of household credit (real estate, consumption, etc.), for lack of sufficient data availability. We use fine-grained data by deciles, enabling us to calculate both the Gini and changes in the respective shares of the highest income earners, the middle classes and the working classes¹⁰. This shows that inequality does indeed contribute to credit expansion, particularly when the share of income held by the middle classes declines.

Sidebar

Databases used in Bazillier et al. (2017a)

For income inequality, the WIID database compiles the main existing databases for 161 countries, covering the period 1867-2015. It brings together and compares data from multiple sources (national institutions, Eurostat, OECD, Luxembourg Income Study (LIS), TransMonEE, CEQ, SEDLAC, etc.), by

each time specifying the level of quality, the unit of measurement, the population concerned, the type of income and whether it is before or after taxes and transfers. This database provides a synthetic indicator of inequality, the Gini index, but also makes it possible to visualize the dynamics of inequality with a decomposition by deciles. In Bazillier *et al* (2017a), we impose data selection rules that ensure comparability between and within countries. This database has the advantage of data transparency, unlike the competing Standardized World Income Inequality Database (SWID), which relies heavily on linear interpolation. We also prefer it to the World Top Income Database (WTID), which focuses on pre-tax income.

In terms of credit data, we have mainly used the BIS database and, occasionally, data from the World Bank, domestic central banks and Oxford Economics. This allows us to break down aggregate credit in a number of ways, by type of lender (bank or non-bank, domestic or non-domestic), or borrower (corporate or household). On the other hand, problems of data quality and availability prevent the conclusive use of consumer credit or mortgage indicators.

The econometric estimation strategy on which these results are based consists of two stages. First, by estimating an inequality equation as a function of a third variable (the instrumental variable), we can extract the "exogenous" part of inequality variations, i.e., the part that is independent of credit dynamics (reverse causality), but also of phenomena that may have influenced both variables simultaneously (the confounding factor). Secondly, we link the credit/GDP ratio to variations in inequality predicted by the instrumental variable. For the latter, we have chosen the number of International Labour Organization (ILO) conventions ratified by each country each year.

The robustness of our estimates therefore rests on two conditions concerning these ILO conventions: they must be globally independent of the dynamics specific to each country, but they must also have a direct impact on inequalities. With regard to the first condition, the period studied (1970-2014) includes two global waves of ratifications due to political

impulses specific to the ILO. Firstly, in the 1970s, the launch of the "International Program for the Improvement of Working Conditions and the Working Environment", together with the dispatch of teams to Africa, Latin America, the Caribbean and Asia, led to a significant increase in the number of ILO conventions signed, particularly in emerging countries. Similarly, in the 1990s, the "International Program for the Elimination of Child Labor" in 1992, targeting over 90 countries, the Copenhagen Social Summit in 1995 and the "Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work" in 1998, recognizing core labor standards, led to a new dynamic of ratifications largely independent of country characteristics. With regard to the second condition, an abundance of empirical literature confirms the negative link between the degree of regulation on the labor market and inequality (see, for example, Checchi and García-Peñalosa, 2008). The underlying mechanism is intuitive: a more regulated labor market increases the bargaining power of workers, who can then better preserve their income levels, thereby reducing inequality.

The results of our study confirm this negative impact of the number of ILO conventions signed on inequality: one additional ILO convention, for example, leads to a 0.321 reduction in the Gini index¹¹. But, more importantly, it appears that the variation in inequality induced by the signing of these ILO conventions generates a significant variation of the same sign in the ratio of household credit to GDP. An increase of 1 standard deviation of the Gini index (i.e., a rise in inequality) is associated with a 7 percentage point increase in the "household credit/GDP" ratio. In concrete terms, inequality in the UK, for example, accounts for 30% of the total increase in this ratio between 1970 and 2011. In the United States, rising inequality accounted for 19% of the growth in the "credit/GDP" ratio between 1980 and 2010. For France, we explain around 22% of the total rise in the ratio.

"credit to GDP" between 1995 and 2011

It's important to note that while this causal impact of inequality can be seen in certain measures of total credit distributed to the economy, the same cannot be said of business credit, whose evolution is totally unrelated to that of inequality. If the rise in inequality leads to a rise in total credit relative to GDP, this is entirely attributable to credit distributed to households.

The impact of inequality on credit is mainly due to the impoverishment of the middle classes

We then use different measures of inequality to highlight another interesting fact hitherto ignored in the literature: a significant proportion of the demand effects presented above are due to the relative impoverishment of the middle classes. This phenomenon is theoretically validated by our extension of the Kumhof et al. (2015) model, which explicitly distinguishes between working and middle classes. Table 4 (infra) summarizes the major results of our article. In all cases, an increase in inequality leads to a rise in the amount of credit distributed to households, whether as a result of an increase in the share of total income going to the richest, or a reduction in the share going to the middle or working classes, hence the negative sign in the latter two cases. Nevertheless, the effects are heterogeneous and more significant when the middle classes are concerned. Thus, while a 1 standard deviation drop

in the share of the working classes in total income results in a 6.2 point rise in the "household credit/GDP" ratio, the same 1 standard deviation drop in the share of the middle classes results, depending on the definition of the latter, in a 2 to 3 times higher rise in the ratio. The gap is smaller, but remains when relative indicators (i.e. income share ratios) measuring the gap between the rich (Top 10% or 30%), on the one hand, and the middle and working classes, on the other, are studied: the impact is around 30% greater for the former than for the latter. It is therefore the relative impoverishment of the middle classes that has the most substantial quantitative impact in terms of credit growth.

Table 4: Impact of a 1 standard deviation increase in various income inequality indicators on the "household credit/GDP"

Inequality measures Household credit as a percentage of GDP (variation, in percentage points)	
Share of total revenue held by :	
• the richest 10% (Top 10)	+10,3
• the richest 30% (Top 30)	+8,5
• the middle classes (from 30% to 90%)*.	-19,4
• the middle classes (from 30% to 70%)**.	-11,5
• working classes (poorest 30%*** Relative	-6,2
income ratio :	
• "Top 10/middle classes (30% to 90%)	+11,4
• "Top 10/popular classes	+8,6
• "Top 30/middle class (30% to 70%)	+9,9
• "Top 30/popular classes	+7,7

Note: the table plots the variations resulting from the product of the estimated coefficients of an econometric regression presented in detail in Bazillier *et al.* (2017a), with the standard deviations of each of the variables in question. In particular, this enables relevant quantitative comparisons to be made.

*: 3rd to 9th decile not included; **: 3rd to 7th decile not included; ***: up to 3rd decile included. The table reads as follows: a 1 standard deviation increase in the share of total income held by the richest 10% leads to a 10.3-point rise in the "household credit/GDP" ratio. The middle classes are defined alternatively as the intermediate categories between the working classes and the wealthy classes of the Top 30% or the Top 10%.

Source: authors' calculations, based on a sample of forty-one developed and emerging countries, over the period 1970-2014.

These results remain, even when subjected to a number of robustness and falsification tests, such as alterations to the definition of the middle classes, the exclusion of the 2007-2008 crisis and subsequent years from the estimation period, or the use of credit aggregates other than household credit alone. Finally, our results seem to be essentially determined by the dynamics of the developed countries in our sample, where the middle classes have easy access to credit and represent a sufficiently large share of the population to dominate trends in aggregate household credit.

CONCLUSION

The relationships between finance and inequality are numerous, complex and intertwined.

On the one hand, the impact of finance on inequality is difficult to pin down: there is as yet no academic consensus as to the sign of the relationship, with results varying widely depending on whether we focus on the size of the financial sector or on other more specific aspects.

such as deregulation, or the role of banks. In any case, it appears that the impact is highly dependent on the country's institutional context. In the absence of solid institutions, the development of finance can be an opportunity for certain interest groups to capture rents, with negative consequences in terms of inequality. Evidence has also recently emerged that financial deregulation can divert labor and other resources from the productive sector. As far as the distributional impact of financial crises is concerned, the results are so far inconclusive.

On the other hand, results in favor of a positive causal link between inequality and credit expansion have been accumulating steadily for some time now, whether they come from studies of a particular country (the USA, although in this case the exact credit category influenced by inequality is open to debate) or from international data. In this respect, the results put forward by Bazillier et al. (2017a and b) highlight the major role played by the middle classes in the scale of the impact exerted by inequalities on household credit dynamics. These findings have obvious economic policy implications: by fuelling the credit bulge, rising inequality fosters the risk of bubbles and the financial crises that often follow, such as that of 2008-2009. Reducing inequality must therefore be a central objective of public policy.

Finally, it's worth noting that the subject is far from exhausted. Several interesting avenues of research remain to be explored. For example, it remains to be determined which type of credit (short? real estate? etc.) is mainly favored by the development of inequalities. As for the latter, income inequality has so far been the main focus of academic literature on the subject, but wealth inequality could undoubtedly be the subject of useful investigations, particularly with the emergence of new databases in this field, such as the WID.

NOTES

In fact, most of the academic literature on the subject focuses on income inequality and does not consider wealth inequality. This can be explained, on the one hand, by the absence of a clear theoretical channel between wealth inequality and indebtedness and, on the other, by the lack of extensive international data on the subject. This state of affairs could change in the years to come with the emergence of wealth databases - for example, the WID database has recently integrated long wealth series, see <http://wid.world/fr/accueil/>. It should also be noted that some works make useful distinctions between inequalities in income, consumption and function.

The distinction between primary and disposable income (i.e., respectively, before and after taxes and transfers) is not widely discussed in the literature. Empirical studies use one or the other definition, depending on the database used: the WID database (formerly known as the World Top Income Database) is based on pre-tax income data, while the WIID database uses disposable income data. The latter would appear to be the most relevant for achieving the most accurate measure of inequality, which is why we use the WIID database in our own work (Bazillier et al., 2017a and b) presented at the end of this article. Nevertheless, financial development certainly covers an even broader reality, referring to the expansion of stock markets (some research explicitly address this dimension, see, for example, Gimet and Lagoarde-Segot, 2011, also cited below) and that of multiple financial services, such as asset management.

Other studies also conclude that the effects are absent (Law and Tan 2009, on the Malaysian case) or conditional. Arora (2012) shows that the redistributive effects of financial development in India are only observed in urban areas.

Kim and Lin (2011) use the WIID database, while Law and Tan (2012) use SWIID. Throughout this literature, the choice of inequality data has a strong impact on the results obtained. Jenkins (2014) and Solt (2015) discuss the respective characteristics of these two databases.

Financialization is defined as "the growing role of financial incentives, financial markets, financial actors and financial institutions in the management of domestic and international economies" (Epstein, 2005).

Furthermore, it should be noted that transitory income shocks are more likely to affect inequalities within a social group, while permanent income shocks have an impact on inequalities between social groups.

It could, of course, be objected that permanent income theory does not rule out a priori recourse to short-term borrowing in the event of a permanent income shock, if, for example, agents have a high preference for the present and/or prefer to smooth the adjustment of their consumption. Permanent income theory, on the other hand, would predict a massive deleveraging and adjustment of consumption in the following period. However, as we have already indicated, the opposite is true: consumption and indebtedness have continued to rise in tandem.

The instruments used, which are supposed to deal with endogeneity problems, are either lagged variables or institutional indicators such as trade openness, whose lack of linkage with credit levels is debatable.

Ideally, it would be desirable to have household credit data evenly distributed by income decile, but such information is not available for such a large number of countries and for such a long period of time. Like the vast majority of academic papers on the subject, we therefore focus on an aggregate household credit indicator.

The Gini index, or coefficient, takes into account the entire income distribution. It ranges from 0 to 100, with 0 representing perfect equality. While it may seem modest in absolute terms, the figure of a 0.321 reduction is in fact substantial, if we bear in mind that this is the average decrease made possible by the signing of a single additional ILO agreement. It should also be noted that the effect remains regardless of the inequality indicator used.

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